

Newsletter 9 October 2008

Current Status: ALPHA (Stage 4)

We are now at Stage 4, with over 50% of participants having been issued the data required for this stage (Table 1, 2). The output from this Stage is due on the **1st November 2008** for all participants. Please let us know if you cannot meet this deadline. Regardless of the stage you are at, please ensure that when you return data, the following are included:

- **Time-stamped information.**
- **Column heading details.**
- **Parameter details.**

Before starting Stage 4, we would like to know what type of city you envisaged when assigning parameter values for this modelling exercise. For example, was a suburban or city-centre location assumed, an old-European style city or a modern US/Asian city?

If you have not yet confirmed (yes or corrections) the model classifications that were detailed in Newsletter 8, please do this as soon as possible (see Table 2).

Reminder, please do **not share any information with any other participating group, regardless of the stage you are at**; and the data cannot be used for other purposes.

Table 1: Project timetable

Target date	Objective	Status
30 April	Deadline for return of Stage 1 output	On-going
1 May	Land cover data issued (Stage 1.5)*	On-going
31 May	Deadline for return of Stage 1.5 output	On-going
1 June	Urban morph. data issued (Stage 2)*	On-going
30 June	Deadline for return of Stage 2 output	On-going
1 July	Urban materials data issued (Stage 3)	On-going
1 Aug	All site data released (Stage 4)	On-going
1 Oct	Deadline for return of Stage 4 output	On-going

Table 2: Current status of the participating groups

- 2: Stage 1 output and parameters received?
- 3: Stage 1.5 data returned?
- 4: Stage 1.5 Parameters returned?
- 5: Stage 2 data returned?
- 6: Stage 2 parameters returned?
- 7: Stage 3 data returned?
- 8: Stage 3 parameters returned?
- 9: Stage 4 data released?
- 10: Confirmed model classifications?**

Model	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
12	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓
13	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
14	Data not released								
16	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
17	✓	✓							
18	Data not released								
20	Data not released								
21	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
22	✓	✓							
25	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
26		Data not released							
28	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
30	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
31	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
32	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
33	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
35	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
36	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
37	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
39	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
41	Data not released								
42	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
43	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
46	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
47	✓	✓	✓						
49	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
50	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Initial Alpha Stage 1 Results

The remainder of the newsletter summarizes model performance in relation to data for Stage 1 when only the forcing data were provided. Table 3 summarizes the statistical performance using all data for the 18 months period. The data included in this analysis required all the observations to be present to be included. The statistics presented are:

- R² coefficient of determination
- RMSE root mean square error
- MAE mean absolute error
- MBE mean bias error
- RMSE_s systematic root mean square error
- RMSE_u unsystematic root mean square error
- IOA index of agreement

In Table 4 the same statistics are presented but based on using only the last 12 months of the observed data set.

Table 3: Model performance statistics for Stage 1 (Alpha) for 18 months of data. The maximum, minimum, mean and median of the statistical results for each of 23 models are given, by flux.

N=11438		Q*	Q _H	Q _{LE}	ΔQ _S
R ²	Max	0.98	0.88	0.37	0.76
	Min	0.83	0.34	0.00	0.58
	Mean	0.97	0.76	0.15	0.71
	Median	0.98	0.79	0.10	0.72
RMSE (W m ⁻²)	Max	103.2	125.0	62.8	246.0
	Min	28.8	38.6	45.2	54.8
	Mean	40.3	68.1	55.3	81.8
	Median	33.5	63.4	54.7	68.3
RMSE _s (W m ⁻²)	Max	71.1	96.5	62.2	234.8
	Min	2.0	10.1	23.3	4.4
	Mean	15.7	39.3	49.6	37.4
	Median	13.4	38.4	48.1	24.9
RMSE _u (W m ⁻²)	Max	100.7	99.2	44.7	118.8
	Min	27.3	35.9	0.0	31.3
	Mean	35.6	53.8	19.7	66.1
	Median	29.7	49.2	22.3	64.6
MAE (W m ⁻²)	Max	68.1	103.1	39.2	190.2
	Min	13.8	24.3	26.3	34.6
	Mean	24.3	45.8	33.7	55.5
	Median	19.8	41.4	33.3	45.1
MBE (W m ⁻²)	Max	66.6	87.4	8.8	18.8
	Min	-22.4	-2.3	-33.6	-34.4
	Mean	-1.5	26.7	-20.4	-5.4
	Median	-5.2	23.0	-18.2	-5.7
IoA	Max	1.00	0.96	0.74	0.93
	Min	0.95	0.65	0.38	0.02
	Mean	0.99	0.89	0.49	0.84
	Median	0.99	0.90	0.47	0.89

Table 4: As for Table 3 but using only the final 12 months of data.

N=9107		Q*	Q _H	Q _{LE}	ΔQ _S
R ²	Max	1.00	0.89	0.41	0.81
	Min	0.83	0.34	0.00	0.60
	Mean	0.98	0.76	0.17	0.75
	Median	0.99	0.80	0.13	0.77
RMSE (W m ⁻²)	Max	102.9	124.9	58.8	248.7
	Min	12.1	36.7	40.0	49.6
	Mean	29.9	67.5	50.8	77.9
	Median	23.1	62.9	49.8	65.7
RMSE _s (W m ⁻²)	Max	70.5	94.1	58.1	239.9
	Min	1.1	8.0	17.3	3.8
	Mean	15.9	38.4	44.5	38.2
	Median	14.1	37.3	42.2	26.0
RMSE _u (W m ⁻²)	Max	100.7	101.4	44.3	108.6
	Min	9.6	35.1	0.0	29.6
	Mean	22.9	53.7	19.8	61.0
	Median	15.6	49.3	22.2	60.1
MAE (W m ⁻²)	Max	67.1	101.5	36.7	192.5
	Min	8.2	22.4	23.8	30.6
	Mean	20.3	44.8	31.2	52.2
	Median	15.9	40.9	30.5	41.9
MBE (W m ⁻²)	Max	66.6	85.3	10.9	23.0
	Min	-22.9	-3.2	-33.0	-33.7
	Mean	-1.5	25.1	-19.6	-4.4
	Median	-5.0	21.9	-17.0	-5.1
IoA	Max	1.00	0.96	0.76	0.94
	Min	0.95	0.65	0.40	0.01
	Mean	0.99	0.89	0.52	0.86
	Median	1.00	0.90	0.51	0.91

In the following figures the individual model performance statistics are ranked (Table 5) for the 18 month period and the last 12 months of the data set. The data are analysed by time of the day (see newsletter 7):

- whole day
- night
- daytime
- transitional

In each figure, the four fluxes are presented in the following position:

$$\begin{array}{c|c} Q^* & \Delta Q_S \\ \hline Q_H & Q_E \end{array}$$

If you note any discrepancies, please make us aware of these as soon as possible.

Table 5: Summary of the figures presented.

Figure number (18 months)	Figure number (last 12 months)	Time of day
RMSE		
1	21	All
2	22	Night time
3	23	Day time
4	24	Transition
RMSEs		
5	25	All
6	26	Night time
7	27	Day time
8	28	Transition
RMSEu		
9	29	All
10	30	Night time
11	31	Day time
12	32	Transition
MAE		
13	33	All
14	34	Night time
15	35	Day time
16	36	Transition
MBE		
17	37	All
18	38	Night time
19	39	Day time
20	40	Transition

If you have questions, please consult the FAQ section of Newsletter 6 (July, 2008) or contact us at UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk.

Sue Grimmond & Matthew Blakett
Department of Geography, King's College London

This project contributes to:

Funding provided by:

FIGURE 1: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, All data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 2: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Night data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 3: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Day data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 4: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Transition data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 5: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEs, All data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 6: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEs, Night data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 7: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEs, Day data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 8: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEs, Transition data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 9: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEu, All data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 10: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEu, Night data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 11: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEu, Day data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 12: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEu, Transition data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 13: Alpha Stage 1, MAE, All data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 14: Alpha Stage 1, MAE, Night data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 15: Alpha Stage 1, MAE, Day data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 16: Alpha Stage 1, MAE, Transition data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 17: Alpha Stage 1, MBE, All data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 18: Alpha Stage 1, MBE, Night data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 19: Alpha Stage 1, MBE, Day data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 20: Alpha Stage 1, MBE, Transition data (18 months), n = 11438

FIGURE 21: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, All data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 22: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Night data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 23: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Day data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 24: Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Transition data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 25: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEs, All data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 26: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEs, Night data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 27: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEs, Day data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 28: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEs, Transition data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 29: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEu, All data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 30: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEu, Night data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 31: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEu, Day data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 32: Alpha Stage 1, RMSEu, Transition data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 33: Alpha Stage 1, MAE, All data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 34: Alpha Stage 1, MAE, Night data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 35: Alpha Stage 1, MAE, Day data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 36: Alpha Stage 1, MAE, Transition data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 37: Alpha Stage 1, MBE, All data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 38: Alpha Stage 1, MBE, Night data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 39: Alpha Stage 1, MBE, Day data (18 months), n = 9107

FIGURE 40: Alpha Stage 1, MBE, Transition data (18 months), n = 9107